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General Practitioners with an Over-Threshold Number of Patients in Italian Regions

They increased by an average of 140.21% between 2004 and 2020.

ISTAT calculates the number of general practitioners with an over-threshold number of patients in the Italian regions. The variable is defined as the percentage of general practitioners with a number of patients exceeding the maximum threshold of 1,500 patients as set by the general practitioners' contract. The data refer to the period from 2004 to 2020 in the Italian regions.

General Practitioners with an Over-Threshold Number of Patients in Italian Regions in 2020. The analysis of 2020 data on general practitioners with a number of patients exceeding the maximum threshold of 1,500 in Italy highlights significant regional variability, reflecting different challenges and needs within the national healthcare system. Particularly affected are the northern regions, with Lombardy, Trentino-Alto Adige/Südtirol, and Veneto registering the highest percentages, suggesting increased pressure on healthcare services in densely populated areas and potential difficulties in attracting new professionals. In the central regions, the situation varies, with Emilia-Romagna and Tuscany showing high values, while the southern regions and islands, except for Campania, show significantly lower percentages, which might indicate a more balanced distribution of patients or lower pressure on general practitioners. This disparity implies the need for targeted regional strategies to improve access to care, reduce the workload of doctors, and promote an equitable distribution of patients. It is essential to consider specific interventions that take local peculiarities into account, such as incentivizing the training of new doctors, adopting innovative care models, and utilizing telemedicine, to ensure high-quality and equitable healthcare throughout the country.

General Practitioners with an Over-Threshold Number of Patients in Italian Regions from 2004 to 2020. The analysis of data on general practitioners in Italy with an over-threshold number of patients from 2004 to 2020 reveals significant trends and regional disparities that warrant attention. Notably, there is considerable growth in regions like Valle d'Aosta/Vallée d'Aoste and Liguria, where the percentage increase has exceeded 200%, indicating growing pressure on primary care services. Conversely, regions such as Puglia, Calabria, and Sicily have shown more moderate increases, suggesting a relatively more stable situation. These variations reflect differences in demographic dynamics, regional health policies, and the attractiveness of various areas for doctors. The growth in

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the number of doctors with a high patient load might indicate problems in accessibility and quality of primary care, with potential negative impacts on public health. This underscores the importance of targeted interventions by health authorities to ensure an equitable distribution of general practitioners and accessibility to care, addressing the challenges for the sustainability of the Italian healthcare system. Monitoring these trends and implementing effective policies is crucial to improve healthcare and ensure all citizens have access to quality care.

General Practitioners with an Over-Threshold Number of Patients in Italian Macro-Regions from 2004 to 2020. The analysis of data on general practitioners in Italy, focusing on the number of patients exceeding the recommended threshold between 2004 and 2020, reveals a concerning trend at both national and regional levels. Nationally, there is a significant increase of 22.4% in over-threshold doctors, with a percentage growth reaching 141.77%. This increase is particularly marked in the northern regions, with the North-West showing the highest increase (208.67%), followed by the North (194.32%) and the North-East (176.11%). Central Italy also shows notable growth (173.60%), while the Mezzogiorno has a more contained but still significant increase. These data underscore growing pressure on the healthcare system, highlighting challenges related to resource distribution, medical personnel management, and demographic factors. The differences between regions also raise questions of equity in access to care and working conditions for doctors. The increasing demand for medical assistance, combined with regional disparity, requires deep reflection on Italian health policies to ensure equitable and effective care nationwide and support healthcare professionals in their daily commitment to public health.

North-South Differences: A Northern Issue. The data highlight a significant divide between northern and southern Italy in terms of general practitioners with an over-threshold number of patients. Northern regions, including those in the North-West and North-East, show much more marked growth in both absolute and percentage terms compared to the Mezzogiorno, comprising the South and Islands. This divide is reflected in the increase in the percentage of over-threshold doctors, with the North seeing very high increases (194.32% for the North, 208.67% for the North-West, and 176.11% for the North-East), while the Mezzogiorno has much more contained increases, with significantly lower percentage changes (59.62% for the Mezzogiorno, 61.54% for the South, and 57.03% for the Islands). The North-South divide can be interpreted as the result of a combination of factors, including differences in the distribution of healthcare resources, medical personnel management policies, and demographic and socio-economic factors. The North might be more affected by issues such as an aging population and higher demand for healthcare services, leading to an overload for general practitioners. Conversely, the divide might also reflect differences in access to care and the quality of available healthcare services, with potential implications for public health and equity in healthcare across different regions of Italy.

Conclusions. The data show an increase in general practitioners with an over-threshold number of patients. This value grew by an average of 140.21% between 2004 and 2020. From the perspective of macro-regions, we can see that this variable grew much more in the central-northern regions than in the central-southern regions. However, this dynamic could simply be represented by a demographic trend. In fact, the North increases its population, while the southern demographics are in structural deficit. Since the population in Northern Italy is growing much faster than the capacity to train or

attract general practitioners, this results in a significant increase in the analyzed variable. To address the problem of general practitioners in Italy with an over-threshold number of patients, it would be useful to adopt a multidimensional approach involving both economic policies and organizational strategies. Increasing funding for primary care could allow the hiring of additional doctors and nursing staff, better distributing the workload. Furthermore, introducing targeted economic incentives could attract doctors to areas with the greatest need, thus balancing the distribution of professionals across the territory. Promoting specific training for general practitioners and utilizing targeted recruitment strategies are essential to increase the number of available professionals. The adoption of telemedicine as a complement to in-person visits can optimize doctors' time, improving efficiency without sacrificing the quality of care. It is also important to incentivize efficient organizational models in medical practices, facilitating a smoother workflow and optimal patient management. Structural reforms promoting better integration between various levels of care and a more equitable distribution of doctors can significantly help resolve the problem. Finally, a continuous monitoring and evaluation system is crucial to ensure that implemented policies are effective.

Declarations

Data Availability Statement. The data presented in this study are available on request from the corresponding author.

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References

Costantiello, A., & Leogrande, A. (2021). The innovation-employment nexus in Europe. Costantiello, A., & Leogrande, A.(2020). The innovation-employment nexus in Europe. *American Journal of Humanities and Social Sciences Research (AJHSSR)*, 4(11), 166-187.

Leogrande, A., Saponaro, A., Massaro, A., & Galiano, A. M. (2020). A GIS based estimation of quality of life in Italian regions. *American Journal of Humanities and Social Sciences Research (AJHSSR)* e-ISSN.

Costantiello, A., Laureti, L., & Leogrande, A. (2021). The intellectual assets in Europe. *Available at SSRN 3956755*.

Magazzino, C., & Leogrande, A. (2020). Subjective well-being in Italian regions: A panel data approach.

Leogrande, A., Massaro, A., & Galiano, A. M. (2020). The attractiveness of European research systems. *American Journal of Humanities and Social Sciences Research (AJHSSR)*, 4(10), 72-101.

Costantiello, A., & Leogrande, A. (2023). The Impact of Research and Development Expenditures on ESG Model in the Global Economy. *Available at SSRN 4414232*.

Leogrande, A. (2023). The Rule of Law in the ESG Framework in the World Economy. *Available at SSRN 4355016*.

Leogrande, A., Massaro, A., & Galiano, A. M. (2020). The impact of R&D investments on corporate performance in European Countries. *American Journal of Humanities and Social Sciences Research (AJHSSR)*, 4(7), 186-201.

Costantiello, A., & Leogrande, A. (2023). The Role of Political Stability in the Context of ESG Models at World Level. *Available at SSRN 4406997*.

Leogrande, A., Laureti, L., & Costantiello, A. (2022). The Innovation Index in Europe. *Available at SSRN 4091597*.

Laureti, L., Costantiello, A., Matarrese, M., & Leogrande, A. (2022). Enterprises Providing ICT Training in Europe. *Available at SSRN 4021150*.

Leogrande, A., & Costantiello, A. (2023). The Labor Force Participation Rate in the Context of ESG Models at World Level. *Available at SSRN 4466452*.

Costantiello, A., & Leogrande, A. (2023). The Impact of Voice and Accountability in the ESG Framework in a Global Perspective. *Available at SSRN 4398483*.

Laureti, L., Costantiello, A., & Leogrande, A. (2023). The Role of Government Effectiveness in the Light of ESG Data at Global Level. *Available at SSRN 4324938*.

Costantiello, A., Laureti, L., Leogrande, A., & Matarrese, M. (2021). The Innovation Linkages in Europe. *Available at SSRN 3983218*.

Laureti, L., Costantiello, A., & Leogrande, A. (2022). Satisfaction with the Environmental Condition in the Italian Regions between 2004 and 2020. *Available at SSRN 4061708*.

Laureti, L., Costantiello, A., Matarrese, M., & Leogrande, A. (2022). Foreign Doctorate Students in Europe. *Available at SSRN 4032975*.

Laureti, L., Costantiello, A., Matarrese, M., & Leogrande, A. (2022). The Employment in Innovative Enterprises in Europe. *Available at SSRN 4010098*.

Leogrande, A., Costantiello, A., Laureti, L., & Leogrande, D. (2021). The Determinants of Landscape and Cultural Heritage Among Italian Regions in the Period 2004-2019. *Available at SSRN 3971174*.

Leogrande, A., Massaro, A., & Galiano, A. M. (2020). The Determinants of Innovation in European Countries in the period 2010-2019. *American Journal of Humanities and Social Sciences Research (AJHSSR)*, 4(8), 91-126.

Ferri, G., & Leogrande, A. (2015). Was the Crisis due to a shift from stakeholder to shareholder finance? Surveying the debate.

Laureti, L., Costantiello, A., Massaro, A., & Leogrande, A. (2024). The Role of Renewable Energy Consumption in Promoting Sustainability and Circular Economy: A Data-Driven Analysis. In *Data-Driven Intelligent Business Sustainability* (pp. 360-386). IGI Global.

Leogrande, A., & Costantiello, A. (2023). The Role of GDP Growth in the ESG Approach at World Level. *Available at SSRN 4434206*.

Costantiello, A., & Leogrande, A. (2023). The Regulatory Quality and ESG Model at World Level. *Available at SSRN 4388957*.

Leogrande, A., Magaletti, N., Cosoli, G., & Massaro, A. (2022). Fixed Broadband Take-Up in Europe. *Available at SSRN 4034298*.

Leogrande, A., Costantiello, A., Laureti, L., & Leogrande, D. (2021). The Determinants of Design Applications in Europe. *Available at SSRN 3956853*.

Laureti, L., Costantiello, A., & Leogrande, A. (2021). THE DETERMINANTS OF FIRM INVESTMENTS IN RESEARCH AND DEVELOPMENT. In *IAI ACADEMIC CONFERENCE PROCEEDINGS Education and Social Sciences Business and Economics* (pp. 55-67).

Costantiello, A., & Leogrande, A. (2024). The regulatory quality in the light of environmental, social and governance framework at world level. *Discover Global Society*, 2(1), 1-20.

Magazzino, C., Madaleno, M., Waqas, M., & Leogrande, A. (2024). Exploring the determinants of methane emissions from a worldwide perspective using panel data and machine learning analyses. *Environmental Pollution*, 348, 123807.

Appendix

Percentuale di medici di medicina generale con un numero di assistiti oltre la soglia nelle regioni italiane - 2020

Percentuale di medici oltre la soglia per area - 2004

Percentuale di medici oltre la soglia per area - 2020

Variazione Assoluta 2004-2020

Variazione Percentuale 2004-2020

Variazione Assoluta del numero di assistiti oltre la soglia nelle regioni italiane 2004-2020

Variazione Percentuale del numero di assistiti oltre la soglia nelle regioni italiane 2004-2020